

Hierarchical micro-nanostructuring of polymer films by simultaneous laser interference and diffraction

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Abstract

This study presents a laser-based method for creating hierarchical micro/nanostructures on polymer surfaces. By combining laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS) with microscale diffraction patterns, using a 266 nm Nd:YAG laser and a mask, poly(bisphenol A carbonate) (PBAC) films were patterned. The interference between the

incident laser beam and the light scattered on the surface leads to the formation of LIPSS aligned with laser polarization while, simultaneously, the use of masks with grids of 90 μm square holes induces Fresnel diffraction. The combination of both effects results in the formation of hierarchical structures that incorporate features at both nano- and microscale respectively. Atomic force microscopy revealed LIPSS formation at the square corners and at the center, with periodicities close to the laser wavelength. At low fluences or pulse numbers, only the diffraction pattern of the mask is observed. LIPSS increased hydrophilicity while the combination of diffraction and LIPSS increased the hydrophobicity. Adhesion force measurements, performed using the colloidal probe technique, indicated a significant increase near the structured edges of the irradiated areas, although at the nanoscale the differences are minimal. This study highlights the effective integration of micro and nanopatterns on polymeric surfaces using diffraction masks. Furthermore, it provides valuable information on how laser processing affects the morphology and properties of the surface, including wettability, adhesion, and mechanical properties. The ability to simultaneously modify the micro and nanoscale opens new avenues for the creation of functional polymeric surfaces with applications in various fields such as nanophotonics, biomedicine, and nanoelectronics.

Keywords: laser induced periodic surface structures, diffraction, laser microstructuring, laser nanostructuring, polymer thin films, surface wettability, surface adhesion

1. Introduction

Polymer nanopatterning plays a crucial role in nanotechnology, enabling the creation of functional surfaces for different applications. For instance, in nanophotonics, ordered polymer nanostructures can be used to fabricate photonic crystals or diffractive optical elements that manipulate light at the nanoscale, leading to advancements in optical sensing and light emission [1,2]. In biomedicine, nano/microstructured functional surfaces have shown potential for the development of topographies designed to guide specific cellular responses [3,4]. In nanoelectronics, polymer templates are essential for creating high-density, ordered arrays of inorganic nanomaterials, relevant for memory devices and transistors with enhanced performance [5,6].

In fact, nanostructured polymer surfaces are essential in determining specific functionalities such as adhesion, friction, wettability, and reflectivity [7,8]. A wide range of techniques is available for polymer nanopatterning including lithographic techniques, polymer self-assembly, surface instabilities, and laser techniques [9,10]. Pulsed laser irradiation may lead to topographical changes both at the nano- and microscale depending on parameters such as pulse duration, wavelength, and fluence [11,12]. In particular, different laser approaches may be used to modify the surfaces of materials, including laser ablation [13], laser texturing [14], irradiation through an array of particles [15], direct laser writing [16], laser interference lithography [17], and laser induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS) [18]. In general, manufacturing of hierarchical micro- and nanotopographies is not trivial and typically requires the use of templates [19], the combination of molds with light and breath figure method [20] or the use of different techniques in sequential steps [21]. Regarding the use of laser techniques, they have been used to fabricate molds with micro- and nanostructures that are then employed to obtain replicas in polymers [22,23], LIPSS have been formed on top of different micrometer

sized structures fabricated by direct laser interference patterning (DLIP) [24] in a two-step process, or hierarchical structures have been formed by an approach combining DLIP and direct laser writing [25].

Together with the topographical changes, additional physicochemical modifications may take place upon laser irradiation, for instance, changes in the chemical composition by the introduction of new functional groups [26], graphitization [27], variations in the molecular weight [28], or phase changes [29], to cite some. The combination of all these changes may also affect surface properties relevant to applications, such as wettability [30], surface energy [31], and mechanical and tribological aspects [32,33].

In addition to just the formation of structures at the nanoscale range, it has been reported that some surface properties, as wetting and mechanical response, can be understood and controlled [34,35] by the formation of hierarchical structures both at the micro- and nanoscale. Thus, the presence of hierarchical structures can explain the non-wetting characteristic of water spider legs [36], or the superhydrophobicity of lotus leaves [37].

In this work, we propose a one-step procedure to form combined nano- and microstructures at the surface of a polymer, in particular, poly (bisphenol A carbonate) (PBAC), based on laser-matter interactions. For this purpose, on the one hand, we will form LIPSS. Typically, nanosecond laser pulses induce LIPSS on polymers, which are aligned parallel to the laser polarization and with a period related to the laser wavelength (known as low spatial frequency LIPSS type II, LSFL-II) [38]. Efficient light absorption at the laser wavelength is crucial for LIPSS formation, which often occurs in the UV region for most polymers [39,40].

On the other hand, and simultaneously with the nanoscale LIPSS formation, microstructure fabrication is obtained by irradiation through a transmission electron

microscopy (TEM) grid so that a diffraction pattern is imprinted on the surface of the polymer in a similar way as reported in [41]. Therefore, to induce the formation of hierarchical structures, irradiation through the grid is done in conditions leading to LIPSS formation on PBAC, which have been previously reported [42]. Wettability and adhesion properties of polymer surfaces are analyzed for the surfaces structured under different irradiation conditions.

2. Materials and Methods

Poly (bisphenol A carbonate) (PBAC), Lexan ML3021A, SABIC I-P (Innovative Plastics), $M_w = 44.4 \cdot 10^3 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$, $M_n = 23.5 \cdot 10^3 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ (as revealed by size-exclusion chromatography) was used in this work. Thin polymer films were prepared by spin coating on silicon wafers (100) (Wafer World Inc.). The wafers were previously cleaned with acetone and 2-propanol and then dried under nitrogen flow. PBAC was dissolved in chloroform (Riedel-de Haën, 99%) with a concentration of 20 g/L. A fixed amount of 0.1 mL of polymer solution was instantly dropped by a syringe on a square (typically $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$) silicon substrate placed in the center of a rotating metallic horizontal plate. A rotation speed of 2380 rpm was kept during 30 s, obtaining spin-coated polymer films with a thickness of about 150 nm, determined by measuring by atomic force microscopy (AFM) the step created by removing the film with a razor blade, and average roughness below 1 nm.

Laser irradiation was carried out in ambient air, at normal incidence, with the linearly polarized laser beam of a Q-switched Nd:YAG laser (Lotis TII LS-2131M, pulse duration $\tau = 8 \text{ ns}$, full width at half-maximum) at a repetition rate of 10 Hz. The polymer films were irradiated through a copper TEM grid from Electron Microscopy Sciences with square holes of $90 \mu\text{m}$, placed at a distance of $120 \mu\text{m}$ from the polymer surface. A scheme

of the experimental setup is provided in Figure S1. The fourth harmonic, at a wavelength of 266 nm, was used for the experiments. At this wavelength, PBAC has an absorption coefficient of $18 \cdot 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [42]. Irradiation was performed in static mode.

The morphology of the polymer thin films was characterized by AFM. A Multimode 8 AFM with a Nanoscope V controller (Bruker) was used under tapping mode with NSG-30 probes (NT-MDT). Square images with 512 x 512 pixels resolution were taken. Analysis of the size and shape of the nanometric features was performed with the NanoScope Analysis 1.50 software (Bruker).

Adhesion force was measured by colloid probe atomic force microscopy using the same AFM equipment. For this purpose, we used colloidal probes CPFM_SiO₂-A/Au (NT-MDT) consisting of a colloidal SiO₂ spherical particle with a diameter of 5-9 μm that is attached to a tipless cantilever. To extract absolute values for the forces from experimental data, the cantilever spring constants for each probe were measured by the thermal tune method and found to be around 1 N/m.

For the characterization of the mechanical properties at the nanoscale, the PeakForce Quantitative Nanomechanical Mapping (PF-QNM) method was used, employing also the same AFM equipment. All quantitative measurements were carried out with NSG-30 probes (NT-MDT). The cantilever spring constant was calculated by the Sader method [43] and found to be around 25 N/m. Tip radius was calibrated against a polystyrene standard of known elastic modulus provided by Bruker. The measured value of the tip radius was 8 nm. More details on the protocol used for the measurements can be found in [44].

The water contact angle measurements were carried out at room temperature and ambient humidity using a pocket goniometer PG2 (FIBRO system). The contact angle values were

determined by the sessile drop technique, using deionized water. We deposited 5 μl drops on a dry and clean surface of polymer film. Static contact angle values were measured immediately after the formation of sessile drops of liquid on the surface. Measurements were carried out for ten different samples of each type tested and results were readily averaged.

Chemical changes of the irradiated areas were inspected by Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy using a Perkin-Elmer Frontier spectrometer equipped with a Perkin-Elmer Microscope Spotlight-200i.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Formation of surface nanostructures

The formation of LIPSS on PBAC thin films has been previously reported [42]. When irradiating thin films, the substrate may affect the experimental irradiation parameters leading to optimal LIPSS formation and the characteristics of the LIPSS, although LIPSS will be formed in any case for an efficiently absorbed laser wavelength [45]. LIPSS formation on PBAC deposited on silicon as a function of the laser fluence and of the number of pulses has been previously optimized, and in particular, they have been observed for irradiation in the range 6-10 mJ/cm^2 and for a number of pulses in the range 900-3000. In this study, we choose a fluence of 7 mJ/cm^2 and 1200 pulses [42]. When we irradiate through TEM grids using these conditions, we observe the patterns shown in Figure 1. The surface of the material is modified in the areas that have been exposed to the laser light, i.e., in square areas with a size of 90 μm x 90 μm , as displayed in Figure 1a. Each square is additionally micro- and nanostructured, as can be observed in the AFM height image in Figure 1b.

Figure 1. (a) Optical microscopy image of a PBAC film showing the square areas of $90 \times 90 \mu\text{m}^2$ (darker zones) modified by laser irradiation through a TEM grid. (b) AFM topography image ($110 \times 110 \mu\text{m}^2$) of one of the squares modified by irradiation in a PBAC irradiated with 1200 laser pulses and $7 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$. The arrow indicates the polarization orientation.

If we analyze in detail the areas 1, 2 and 3 in Figure 1b we observe that in the center of the square (Figure 2, area 1), LIPSS parallel to the laser polarization are formed, with a period around $180 \pm 11 \text{ nm}$ and a depth around $46 \pm 14 \text{ nm}$, as can be seen in the profile shown. In this region, there is only one period of the structures. In area 2, corresponding to the left edge of the square, we observe again LIPSS parallel to the laser polarization (horizontal orientation), which are along vertical lines with a width of microns. Between these lines, there is a separation that is not constant but decreases when we are moving inside the square (blue line, area 2, Figure 2). In particular, there is a distance of $5.1 \mu\text{m}$ between the outer line and the second line, which decreases for the following lines down to $3.1 \mu\text{m}$, $2.5 \mu\text{m}$, $2.1 \mu\text{m}$, $1.8 \mu\text{m}$, $1.6 \mu\text{m}$, $1.4 \mu\text{m}$ and to the point that there is a continuum (see blue line). It is also interesting that for the outer line it seems that some

ablation is taking place, since there is a crater, but this removal of material is becoming non-significant for the following lines. Another interesting observation is that LIPSS present in the different lines have different periods as can be observed in the black, red and green profiles shown. A period of 242 ± 25 nm is observed in the outer line (black), of 200 ± 31 nm in the second line (red) and of 191 ± 32 nm in the third line (green). Considering that in the outer regions the nominal fluence is higher due to the diffraction effect, this is in agreement with previous works in which an increase in the period has been observed as the laser fluence increases until a plateau is reached [42,46]. This increase of the period obtained is related to the effective feedback effect, so that the accumulation of successive pulses leads to an increase of the superficial temperature, which in turn generates a softer material with lower superficial viscosity allowing the formation of wider structures characterized by larger periods at higher fluences. Similar structures, with period values decreasing from the outer line to inner lines, are observed in the AFM image corresponding to the area 3 (Figure 2), although in this case LIPSS are parallel to the side of the irradiated square. And again, the separation between lines is not constant but decreases when we are moving inside the square.

Figure S2 shows Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis of images shown in Figure 2. From the images and the corresponding profiles we can extract information about the structures formed and their sizes, and it is also clear from them that there is a distribution of sizes.

Figure 2. AFM topography images of the areas (1)-(3) (left) indicated in Figure 1b and height profiles (right) along several lines as marked. The arrows indicate the laser polarization orientation.

When irradiation takes place at fluences below or above those leading to LIPSS formation, the surface is modified as displayed in Figure 3a and b respectively. In the case of irradiation at a fluence of 5 mJ/cm^2 a topographical modification with features in the microscale as a consequence of diffraction is produced. Regions receiving higher fluence due to diffraction effects also show locally some LIPSS-like structures, as it is the case at the corner of the square displayed in the inset of figure 3a, although LIPSS are not formed in the center of the square. In contrast, irradiation at a fluence of 20 mJ/cm^2 leads to material ablation, particularly near the square edge, where the diffraction effect is more pronounced.

Figure 3. AFM topography images of PBAC irradiated with 1200 pulses and (a) 5 mJ/cm^2 and (b) 20 mJ/cm^2 . Inset in (a) shows a detailed image of $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$.

The formation of this kind of structures, combining both LIPSS and a micropattern, can be explained by the fact that the laser light intensity is modulated by diffraction in the square apertures of the TEM grid. Computer-simulated Fresnel diffraction images representing the laser intensity distribution on the polymer film were obtained using the Fresnel integrals approach following [47]. In brief, the diffracted intensity from a plane light wave over a square aperture is observed on a screen located at a certain distance from the aperture. Using the Huygens–Fresnel principle, the total electric field at any given point of the image plane by summing up the contributions of all the elementary wavelets (which are not plane in this case) emitted by different areas inside the square aperture. Integration of the contributions of the elementary Huygens wavelets emitted from an area element over the entire area of the square aperture, allows the calculation of the total electric field and the intensity at a certain point in the screen. For the calculation, we considered a laser wavelength of 266 nm, and an aperture dimension of $90 \times 90 \mu\text{m}^2$. Computer-simulated Fresnel diffraction images representing the laser intensity distribution on the polymer film were obtained following [47] and Figure 4 displays the simulated intensity distribution (top layer) together with the AFM image of a region of a PBAC film irradiated through the TEM grid (bottom layer). The distance of the TEM grid to the polymer film is considered to be $120 \mu\text{m}$. From the comparison between both images, it is clear that there is a good agreement between the theory and the experiment.

Additionally, Figure S3 shows the simulated intensity distribution of the complete square and the profile along the horizontal direction. It is observed that the intensity in the central area is almost constant and modulation minimized, which is in agreement with LIPSS formation in that area, but it can also account for the formation of LIPSS that are not completely uniform. In more detail, the comparison of the simulated diffracted intensity and the height obtained from the AFM image in Figure 4 is displayed in Figure S4. Higher

intensity corresponds to a higher modification on the polymer surface, leading to ablation in the regions closer to the square edge.

Figure 4. Simulated intensity distribution (top layer) and AFM image (bottom layer) of a region of a PBAC film irradiated through the TEM grid.

3.2. Surface properties

As mentioned, three different techniques were used in order to study the surface properties in terms of adhesion and mechanical properties. These techniques will give information at different length scale. Contact angle measurements allows us obtaining information of larger areas in the millimeter scale, while the use of colloidal probes

provides information in the microscale and PF-QNM is suitable for mapping at the nanoscale.

3.2.1. Contact angle measurements

The contact angle measurements are related to the strength of non-covalent forces between the liquid and the outer surface of the tested solid. Thus, in the case of strong interactions between the two phases, the liquid drop spreads on the solid surface and wets it. Figure 5 shows images corresponding to water drops on different PBAC surfaces. The water contact angle of pristine spin-coated PBAC is 85° , which means that the material is slightly hydrophilic. After LIPSS formation, the contact angle decreases, i.e., the surface becomes more hydrophilic. This observation could be explained considering the Wenzel model ($\cos(\theta^*)=r \cdot \cos(\theta)$, where θ^* is the apparent contact angle and r is a roughness factor >1) [48]. Applied to an intrinsic hydrophilic material, if the surface roughness increases (due to the formation of LIPSS in this case), a smaller water contact angle is achieved, increasing the hydrophilicity of the surface. In particular, while the initial average roughness (R_a) of the polymer film is 0.5 ± 0.1 nm, the R_a of a surface with LIPSS increases to 14 ± 1 nm.

However, in the case of surfaces with microstructures, as a consequence of diffraction alone, or hierarchical nano/microstructures, combined with LIPSS, the water contact angle increases indicating an increase of the hydrophobic character. Considering that irradiation dose is the same (both fluence and irradiation time) and then, the extent of the chemical modification would be the same, differences should be explained by the different topographies. Thus, while the nanostructured surfaces become more hydrophilic, which could be explained assuming a homogeneous wetting model for water, Wenzel's model, incorporating micrometric features, changes the wetting regime,

explained in this case by the Cassie-Baxter model. According to this model, the secondary microstructure is more efficient in creating “air-pockets” on the surface, reducing in this way the effective surface contact and then leading to an increased water contact angle [49]. Additionally, it should be considered that while in the case of samples with LIPSS we have the irradiated area (5 mm diameter) homogeneously modified with these nanostructures, in the case of samples irradiated through the TEM grids there is an additional microstructure if we consider the squares of 90 μm size (Figure 1a).

Chemistry also affects the wettability, and it has been previously reported that a slight oxidation at the very outer part of the material induced by laser irradiation may be induced when LIPSS are formed upon irradiation of polymers in air [50]. This chemical modification would also favor the hydrophilic behavior. We have carried out micro-FTIR spectroscopy analysis, and we have recorded the typical PBAC spectra of the non-irradiated areas according to the literature [51]. Then, spectra at different irradiated areas have been taken, and we have observed that there are no significant differences between the irradiated and non-irradiated surfaces or between the central and the edge of every square (Figure S5). As we are inspecting the whole thickness of the polymer film, we could assume that in case of inducing any chemical modification, this will take place in a very superficial way.

Figure 5. Images of a water drop on different PBAC surfaces as labelled (top row) and contact angle values for the different samples (bottom row).

3.2.2. Adhesion force measurements by colloidal probe technique

Adhesion force measurements were performed at different positions of the sample along the modified area in order to obtain information of the effect of different structures on the adhesion force. In this way, curve forces out of the modified area and along the modified square were recorded. Measurements were carried out at three different squares in each case. Adhesion force measured in pristine PBAC is 8 ± 2 nN.

Figure 6a shows the values of adhesion force along the modified squares for a sample irradiated with 1200 pulses at 7 mJ/cm^2 , in which both micro- and nanostructures are observed. In addition, figure 6 shows the adhesion force values for a sample where microstructures induced by diffraction is the only topographical effect. In Figure S6, the force curves at each position of a square in the case of the sample irradiated with 1200 pulses at 7 mJ/cm^2 are shown. It can be observed that in the case in which micro- and nanostructure are present in the sample, a “periodic” variation on the adhesion force is observed in a region of around $15 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ close to the edge. Adhesion force increases up to values of around 40 nN . This area corresponds to the region in which hierarchical structures, combining micrometer lines with LIPSS are produced. The differences could be ascribed to the different contact area when inspecting this region [52]. On the contrary, values obtained in the center of the square, where only LIPSS are formed, are similar to those corresponding to the non-irradiated PBAC.

In the case of the sample irradiated at a lower fluence, i.e., only a diffraction effect is observed with exception of a region very close to the edge with LIPSS, the adhesion force remains practically constant along the square. Only at a short distance from the edge, where LIPSS appear, an increased adhesion force ($\approx 15 \text{ nN}$) is measured. An increase in the adhesion properties of materials modified by laser irradiation has been previously reported [53,54].

Figure 6. Adhesion force corresponding to areas irradiated with 1200 pulses at (a) 7 mJ/cm² and (b) 5 mJ/cm². As reference, AFM height images, with lines indicating where adhesion force measurements were carried out are shown.

3.2.3. Quantitative nanomechanical properties

Figure S7 shows the PFM-QNM images corresponding to the PBAC film irradiated with 1200 pulses and a fluence of 7 mJ/cm², taken at a 75 nN peak force. The surface nanomechanical properties measured by PF-QNM, i.e., Young's modulus, adhesion and deformation maps, showed homogeneous distributions for the non-irradiated areas, and the average values for these flat areas are listed in Table 1. For this, measurements were taken at three different positions.

Table 1. Nanomechanical mean values for Young's modulus, adhesion force, and deformation for the sample micro- and nanostructured (Figure 8) in comparison to the pristine one.

	Young's modulus (GPa)	Adhesion force (nN)	Deformation (nm)
Non-irradiated	2.5 ±0.2	6.4 ±0.4	1.6 ±0.1
Irradiated at 7 mJ/cm²	3.4 ±0.4	8 ±1	1.1 ±0.1

Specifically, the average Young's modulus of PBAC was 2.5±0.2 GPa, similar to the one reported previously for thin films (2.40–2.65 GPa) [55] or commercially available PBAC (~2.4 GPa) [56]. Adhesion values are similar to those obtained by the colloidal probe technique.

We then measured in detail smaller areas at the center of the structured region, as displayed in Figure 7. Unlike the uniform mechanical properties seen in non-irradiated samples, the nanostructured films exhibited spatially varying mechanical characteristics that correlated strongly with their surface topography, an effect that we reported previously for other polymer films [44]. In particular, we observed discrepancies in Young's modulus, adhesion, and deformation between the slopes of the LIPSS and their peaks and valleys. This can be attributed to the limitations of the contact mechanics model employed, which assumes a spherical indenter interacting with a flat, infinite surface, with contact occurring solely in the normal direction. While the peaks and valleys, despite their curvature, approximate this condition due to their relatively large radii of curvature compared to the indenter tip, the slopes of the LIPSS deviate significantly. At these slopes, the contact deviates from the assumptions of normal indentation onto a flat

surface, rendering the values obtained for nanomechanical properties unreliable. The severity of this discrepancy increases with the aspect ratio of the nanostructures, as the deviation from the model's assumptions becomes more pronounced. The differences can be observed in the Figure S8. For this reason, we just averaged the values corresponding to the top of the LIPSS, and summarized them in Table 1. As can be observed, the formation of nanostructures, led to an increase of the surface Young's modulus, together with a decrease of the deformation, which could indicate that laser nanostructuring improves the mechanical properties, in a similar way to what previously reported for other polymer-based materials [44]. Adhesion values are similar although slightly higher than to those corresponding to the flat sample, as reported also in the previous section.

The fact that there are different properties in the nanoscale and the microscale if we compare the results of this section with the ones shown in the previous one, could be related to different interactions between the AFM tip and the nano- and microstructures. The tip interacts with the nanoscale patterns (produced by LIPSS) through a certain contact area, while the presence of micrometric features can enhance this effective contact area and, as a result, the increased surface interaction leads to a higher measured adhesion force. Thus, although changes at the nanoscale are small, the combination of micro and nanostructures enhances the effect, and we detect significant changes both in adhesion and wettability, which is also “sensing” large areas and not solely the presence of nanostructures (LIPSS).

Figure 7. 5 μm x 5 μm PF-QNM images (height, surface elastic modulus, adhesion and deformation) of PBAC laser nanostructured using 1200 pulses at a fluence of 7 mJ/cm².

4. Conclusions

This study presents an innovative and straightforward method for producing hierarchical nano-microstructures using laser irradiation. The irradiation of PBAC thin films through diffraction masks allows the simultaneous formation of microstructures based on Fresnel diffraction and LIPSS nanostructures, opening a range of possibilities in the design of functional surfaces. It has been shown that modulation of the laser light intensity by using

TEM grids generates well-defined diffraction patterns on the polymer surface. These patterns can be controlled by adjusting the laser parameters, allowing the creation of surface structures with different morphological characteristics. Thus, for fluences up to 5 mJ/cm², only modifications due to diffraction are formed although with a contrast of a few nanometers, in the range 6-10 mJ/cm² both well defined LIPSS and patterns due to diffraction are observed and for higher fluences only diffraction-related structures are observed although may also take place.

The research reveals that LIPSS nanostructures increase the hydrophilicity of the surface, decreasing the contact angle of water. In contrast, the combination of microscale diffraction patterns with nanoscale LIPSS produces an increase in hydrophobicity, offering precise control over the wetting properties of the surface.

Adhesion force measurements show a significant increase in the structured edges of the irradiated areas, where combined micro and nanoscale structures are formed. This finding highlights the potential of this method for controlled modification of adhesion properties on polymeric surfaces. Nanometer-scale variations have minimal effects on adhesion.

Understanding how laser processing affects the morphology and properties of surfaces, such as wettability, adhesion and mechanical properties, is crucial for the development of advanced materials. This study generated linear LIPSS, but using different laser polarizations or custom-designed masks could create varied nano- and microscale structures. The versatility of this technique allows the design and fabrication of surfaces with tailored properties, making it a valuable tool for future innovations in materials science and nanotechnology.

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